

Towards Curbing the Two Pristine Musketeers in the Nigerian Political Space

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Abstract

It is of immense interest to note that the independent and post independent political space in Nigeria is controlled by religion and ethnicity. These two musketeers have dovetailed into virtually other aspects of governance and bureaucratic sectors. In point of fact, these two musketeers brought about incompetent leaders, unqualified leaders, bad governance, religious bigotry, ethnic sentiment and amongst others. The aim of this study is to ensure curbing religion and ethnicity in the Nigerian political space. Whereas the objectives are to critique religion and ethnicity in the light of the political unwholesomeness in Nigeria. The research methods employed in this paper include historical and descriptive approach. The historical method will help to trace the origin of the two pristine musketeers, while the descriptive approach will help to elicit information through qualitative method. The study seeks to posit that the current political quagmire in contemporary Nigeria is heightened by religious cum ethnic fangs. The study concludes that religion and ethnicity should be kept away from public policies and Nigerian governance. Therefore, the paper recommends that Nigeria should rather utilize the tenets of religion to help stabilize the country than promoting religion and ethnicity.

Keywords. Religion, Ethnicity, Nigeria, Political space, Musketeers

Introduction

Nigeria, as a nation has been experiencing socio-political convulsion on the basis of religion and ethnicity as the two pristine musketeers. The independent and post-independent Nigeria is not an exception from this political miasma. It is clear that leadership in all tiers of Nigerian government on the basis of religion and ethnicity, has successfully dislodged the good ancient and traditional system of merit, credible and competent leadership at the altar of ethnic sentiments, religious persuasion, prejudice, ignorance and parochialism. As a diverse and heterogenous nation, two or three geo-political zones have been producing leadership since the first republic till date. The aftermath of the promotion of religion and ethnicity in the Nigerian political space is the triumph of mediocrity, incompetent, unpopular and irrational leaders. It is therefore the thrust of this paper to examine religion and ethnicity as the two musketeers by juxtaposing them and well discussing the implications in the Nigerian political space.

A Synopsis of Religion as a Concept

Religion as a concept and phenomenon is open to various meanings and interpretations. Different approaches have been introduced into its study. This reason makes it academically tasking to offer a universally acceptable definition. Be that as it may, the word religion is derived from a Latin word “*religare*” and it etymologically means “to bind”, to bring together, to come together to exist side by side and to fuse people together.¹ Some scholars have correctly observed that religion is that particular phenomenon that brings people together. As far as it has the propensity of bringing people together, it is within the province or agora of religion.² Religion by extension is all-encompassing and all-embracing.

Ilega defines religion as a concept that is all embracing and can bring people together, no matter their differences, to embrace each other and live peacefully with a common agenda for the progress of a nation.³ In a similar sense, the *Chamber 20th Century Dictionary* describes religion as “belief in, recognition of an awakened sense of a higher unseen controlling power or with the emotion and morality connected therewith”.⁴ The above

view has brought into the fore the concept of unseen controlling power or powers with emotion and morality, which some theologians and other scholars would regard as God, Supreme Being or Transcendent or Supersensible Being. Kenny as quoted by Ayantayo aptly describes religion” as any system which relates men to ultimate values, whether God or something else and which embodies, a creed, a code and a cult.⁵ Again, Keqley as cited by Ayantayo distinguishes three basic features of religion as belief, feeling and action. It is of interest to note that what is central to religion is belief in God or gods, the nature and destiny and the meaning of history and the end. We come to appreciate the fact that religion does not only command loyalty, but also gives its adherents something they are glad to live for and if need be, die for.⁶ In like manner, Ejiofor attests to the fact that: “Religion is the complex of belief and behaviour of man in the Supernatural Sphere and realities and in the dynamic linkage of supernatural with the natural... Religion is the major drive behind human behaviour. Religion has had an important disciplinary effect on the whole social order in any given civilization.”⁷

Religion is a very deep factor in the lives of mankind. As a matter of fact, religion identifies itself with the first instinct for self-preservation. According to Ejiofor “Men take off from religion, march along with religion and they arrive at religion with a minute-to-minute phenomenon”.⁸ He further buttresses the fact that religion is the pride of the mind, the strength of the will, the relish of human emotions and coveted object of delicate sentimentality. In short, it is the comprehensive résumé of man’s spiritual, rational and corporate existence.⁹ Kukah opines that religion is an explanation of it within the context of a set of rituals by which the human beings relate with the higher being has come to be accepted while its derivation from the Latin word ‘*religare*’ (to bind) has come to be understood as reflecting the effort by fallen man to re-establish contact with his creator.¹⁰ Religion is a delicate issue; but as sensitive and volatile as it is worth living for, a pride of place for people as they derive satisfaction from it, as well as a sense of security.¹¹

Ethnicity: A Panoramic Overview

Ethnicity can be approached as a socially used cultural symbol of complementarity of “we are what they are not”¹². Ethnicity, according to Nnoli, may be regarded as a social phenomenon associated with interactions among members of different ethnic groups.¹³ Ethnic groups are social formations distinguished by communal character. Gbade asserts that ethnicity is characteristically a common consciousness of being one in relation to other significant groups. This relevance becomes evident in their language, culture or both.¹⁴ It is vital to add that ethnic groups are cultural not natural groups. Salamone argues that ethnic groups are quite simple groups organized around the principles of common descent. The progress of this degree to which this difference is tolerated, respected, or even ignored is dependent on a number of factors; racial difference, religious beliefs and practices, occupational opposition or complementarity, and a thousand of other factors human cultures can invent or give salience to.”¹⁵ Francis cited by Olayode, remarks that ethnicity has cultural affinities that manifest in shared linguistics, religious, racial or other faces, which enable one community to differentiate itself from others.¹⁶ This entails people’s loyalty to and identification with a particular ethnic nationality groups within a nation state.

A Juxtaposition of Religion and Ethnicity in Nigerian Political Space

In the annals of Nigerian political history, religion and ethnicity have been the musketeers that spice up the nation’s polity. Indubitably, the creation of political party is drawn along ethnic and religious persuasion. Put differently, the geography of politics in Nigeria is the geography of religion.¹⁷ In the pre-independent Nigerian State, the amalgamation by the colonial overlords failed to unify the Northern and Southern protectorates; rather, it was an unholy, incompatible and inconvenient marriage that has so far jeopardized our common existence. Kukah argues that:

Colonialists did not help in sharpening the boundaries of prejudices which have now come to dominate our landscape. In Nigeria, for example, British colonialism was enamoured with the Fulani whom they believed were imbued with leadership qualities. This thinking... later took root

in the midst of the Fulani and made them unresponsive to the quest of other citizens for a place in the power ladder in Nigeria.¹⁸

Sequel to the above, the boundaries of prejudices have given impetus to Northern hegemony by asserting its ethnic superiority over ethnic minority of the South. Besides, the struggle for power, dominance and control by Northern hegemony are further consolidated by the advent of Islam. However, Kukah again asserts that the foundation stone of Hausa/Fulani hegemony in the Nigerian polity was the consolidation of Islam through the Jihad of 1804 of Uthman Dan Fodio that legitimizes the expansion of Islam.¹⁹

Although, the advents of Islam and Christianity in Nigeria vary significantly with the regard to historical and cultural experiences, when both Islam and Christianity arrived at the shore of the Nigerian soil, they sought to assert themselves by dislodging the indigenous religion of the people and offered them their new gods as a basis of moral legitimation.²⁰ The adherents of the indigenous religion have consistently maintained a long history of co-operative interaction with Christianity and Islam in Nigeria.²¹ This principle of 'live and let live' has been fostered by the adherents of the indigenous religion despite the derogatory nomenclatures perpetrated by the adherents of proselytizing religion of Islam and Christianity. In other words, the cooperative interaction fostered by the followers of indigenous religion, was truncated by the adherents of both Islam and Christianity, who promoted and still promote superiority, particularity, fanaticism and contestation of space.

There is scintilla of reason to recall that the geography of religion paved way for the consolidation of ethnic supremacy with other favoured ethnic groups as minority, South interjecting into the geography of political parties before independence in 1960. This politicking snowballed into the creation of different parties such as Action Group (AG), Northern People's Congress (NPC) and National Congress for the Nigerians and Comeroons (NCNC). Apart from religious interest of these parties, ethnicity became the driving force from the outset, while in the 1970s, the likes of Unity Party of Nigeria (UPN) replaced Action Group, National Party of Nigeria (NPN) and Nigerian Peoples Party (NPP) replaced former Northern People Congress (NPC), while People's Redemptive Party (PRP) and National Advanced Party (NAP) shared some tides with the North and middle-belt. In retrospect, Action Group (AG) had Yoruba Nationality, which was not in the majority party. Northern People's Congress was predominantly North in the majority, while (NCNC) was the Easterners which also falls in the minority group.

In the 1990s, General Ibrahim Babangida floated two parties namely Social Democracy Party (SDP) and National Republican Convention (NRC). The former belonged to the Southern ethnic minority while the latter belonged to the Northerners who are in the Majority. Late Sanni Abacha, before his demise also established his five political parties. General Abdulsalami Abubakar established People Democratic Party (PDP), All People's Party (APP) that metamorphosed to All National People Party (ANPP), and later developed to All Progressive Congress (APC), Advanced Democracy (AD) and other parties.²²

Since Nigerian Independence, fifteen leaders who could be traced to same religious and ethnic stocks have emerged. Suffice it to name them chronologically. Tafawa Abubakar Balewa, 1960-1966, JFU Aguiyi Ironsi – January 1966-July 1966, Yakubu Gowon 1966-1975, Muritala Mohammed 1975-76, Olusegun Obasanjo 1976-1979, Shehu Aliu Shagari 1979-1983, Muhammadu Buhari, 1983-85, Ibrahim Babangida, 1985-August 1993, Ernest Shonekan August 1993-November, 1993, Sanni Abacha 1993-1998, Abdulsalami Abubakar 1998-1999, Olusegun Obasanjo 1999-2007, Umaru Musa Yar'Adua, 2007-2010, Jonathan Goodluck, 2010-2015, Muhammadu Buhari 2015 till date. The above has shown that out of the fifteen Nigerian leaders, ten are predominantly Northerners. This had further buttressed the dominance of Northern political hegemony. Ovwasa and Idowu have opined that in the political arena, there have been a Northern domination and monopoly of political power at the expense of the other region.²³ Even in the face of Nigerian Federal Character and the purported six geo-political zones formula, religious and ethnic learnings of the Northern hegemony hold sway.

The issue of dominance is fundamental to them, and they re-echo it as a password. Kukah recently reiterates the statement of Sultan of Sokoto who said that "let the Northern elite who have surrendered the space claim it back immediately."²⁴ In 1995, Alhaji Maitama Sule, one of the Nigeria's respected bureaucrats created a

storm among Southern intellectuals when he noted that different communities in Nigeria were differently endowed: the Fulani with leadership qualities, the Igbo with industry and the Yoruba with diplomatic skills.²⁵ All these point to the fact that the Northerners see leadership and power as their birth right. The issue of ethno-religious factor, especially in the post-independence has assumed a new apparel that murders the process of development. Promoting and advertising religion and ethnicity in the nation's polity, permit incompetent, unpopular and irrational leadership that explains away the beauty of diversity in Nigeria.

Implications of Religion and Ethnicity on the Nigerian Nation

Exploring the interplay of religion and ethnicity in the politics of the Nigerian nation has shown that it has caused more damages to the polity, balkanized federalism and caused a lot of setbacks to the nation. The politics of ethno-religiosity in Nigerian has already consumed both the wielders and the targets. To show that it is unhealthy to employ ethno-religiosity in Nigerian politics, Kukah bemoans that political mobilizers have become arrogant in exploring and exploiting religion to their own advantage, which is a minus to the nation.²⁶ It is of essence to note that Nigeria as a nation has been in open confrontation since her creation and amalgamation by the colonial overlords. The implication has been the tussle between the North and the South, as well as between Islam and Christianity. In addition, the supremacy of the North for power, dominance and control led to the balkanization of federal or regional system of government in our nationhood.

Despite the fact that the Northerner is ruling, there are no answers to the plight of millions of young children on the streets in Northern Nigeria; the North still has the worst indices of poverty, insecurity, stunting, squalor and destitution.²⁷ Moreover, a social media commentator did not only blame religion and ethnicity on the basis of non-performance, but also blame the Southerners, especially the Yoruba for their collaboration. According to the commentator,

We are all contributors to the very hopeless situation we have now in the country. We complain about our leaders but when the opportunity to make choices come, we rally round religion, ethnicity and other mundane interests. Many of us are also non-challant on this issue, only a few thinks of competence while making choices concerning those who lead us and determine our present and future existences. We then invoke God or pray to God when we begin to suffer the dire consequences of our choices. The situation has never improved, and will not, otherwise, why hasn't God answered all these years? I have heard this prayer point since I was in primary school but things have gone worse.²⁸

So far, we have seen that religion and ethnicity as the two musketeers have been powerful weapon, used by the North against the South. This has opened up rooms for mediocre, dullards and irrational leaders to govern Nigeria with impunity. Machi posits that anyone who promotes ethnicity than nation should consider such a nation a failed one.²⁹

Towards Curbing the Musketeers in the Nigerian Political Space

Wole Soyinka has advocated that religion should be privatized in Nigeria.³⁰ In the same vein, El Mahdi asserts that religion should be shut out of politics and public life, while national integration is required by the development of the political system.³¹ In spite of the fact that these scholars have advocated for national integration, the true talk remains that religion and ethnicity are a thriving political force in under-developed societies. It is out of place politically to think that primordial phenomenon of religion and ethnicity can be totally erased in the Nigerian political space. Both Christians and Muslims lack a united voice and moral authority to address, for example, the issue of corruption in the polity, abuse of power and moral decadence.³²

Since El Mahdi advocates for national integration as one of the changes required by the development of political system, this can only be evident in religious re-orientation and patriotism as the weapons to cage the musketeers. Our excursion has shown vividly that religion and ethnicity are recipes for strife within the religious communities itself, between different creeds, and indeed a prelude to international polarization and conflict. To

notice such hazards and so attempt to expel religion from public life is equivalent to throwing the baby with the bath water.³³ Instead, some noble ideals of religion should be tapped and harnessed for good governance. El Mahdi supports the fact that the challenge before our nation is to recognize religious worth in its own right and so achieve divine blessing, and harness the considerable religious energy in nation building and national development.³⁴

Patriotism energises and makes us seek to remake the world in the way we believe God wanted it to be. If we love our nation, we will be concerned about how it is administered and by whom? If we love our nation, we will be concerned about whether those in authority exercise their power in the way God Himself would be happy.³⁵ When this patriotism is permitted and becomes front burner, then politics to us like Kukah rightly posits becomes the art of managing the fruits of God's gift to humanity, an equitable management of the abundance of humanity that is God's children and the art of restraining the strong and the greedy from destroying the weak. This is the vision of politics in the mind of God, not our selfish nature which has turned politics into the art of exploitation.³⁶

Lastly, international politics or interference should be resisted by all means. Pope John Paul II corroborates this idea when he states that "it is my conviction that Africa when allowed to take charge of its own affairs without being subjected to interference and pressure from outside by its achievements, but be able to share its wisdom, its sense of life, its reverence for God with other continents and nations, thus establishing that it is exchange and partnership in mutual love of the part of God's earth."³⁷

Conclusion

The horrific of today's political system in Nigeria is central to religion and ethnicity. The consequences of this are regrettably divisive, insensitive, rudderless, precarious and anti-progressive. The travail of the ever-with-us political structure in Nigeria is the trauma and dilemma of incompetent and unpopular leadership we currently experience in Nigeria. The study has advocated that national integration as couched in the reappraisal of noble religious ideals, patriotism and non-interference from external forces. Once, these noble ideals are put to use religiously, no doubt, Nigeria will be wriggled out of the current political quagmire and becomes a success story.

Endnotes

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